

1 ILVO eDNA (GBIF) dataset landing page

2 Taxonomic backbone

Sample occurrence record (*M. merlangus*) - GBIF

List of taxon identifiers from Catalog of Life, NCBI, GBIF, FishBase, WoRMS...

3 Biodiversity data publishing

Sample occurrence record (*M. merlangus*) - GBIF

4 Processed sequence data

Sample occurrence record (*M. merlangus*) - GBIF

DNA sequence, primers, institution, sample size Unit and Value, and identifying person

5 Reference libraries / bioinfo pipeline

GBIF dataset landing page

No findable reference library was linked or given in occurrence record. Bioinfo pipeline is only described in-text (under "methodology") with no linkage to a standard, stable pipeline.

5. Bioinformatic processing The quality of the raw Illumina MiSeq sequencing reads was verified with FASTQC v0.11.9. The paired-end reads were then reorientated, demultiplexed and trimmed by using cutadapt. After demultiplexing, DADA2 was used for denoising, dereplication, merging, and removing of chimeric reads from the demultiplexed sequences. The taxonomic assignment of the resulting ASV sequences was performed against a custom made reference database using RDP classifier in DADA2 with a minimum bootstrapping support of 80. ASVs that remained unassigned at species level with RDP were successively run with BLASTn v2.12.0 against the custom made reference databases and the GenBank nucleotide database (from October 2022). After taxonomic assignment, the count table was cleaned by removing all the ASVs identified as contaminant by the prevalence method in Decontam using the field, filter, DNA extraction and PCR negative control samples.

URL: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/8fd84a4f-bbed-490b-9ca4-c0a3d0aea079#methodology>

DADA2 pipeline is findable and open-access, but unfindable / inaccessible reference database makes study not replicable at present.

6 Raw sequence data

GBIF sample occurrence record → NCBI SRA

7

Laboratory sequencing protocols

NCBI BioProject → Open access article

National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

URL: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject?LinkName=sra_bioproject&from_uid=30751364

BioProject

Display Settings: ▾

BioProject record linked from the raw sequence record in previous step

Links from SRA

Seawater from the North Sea Accession: PRJNA1032405 ID: 1032405

Seawater from the North Sea Raw sequence reads

As part of the Zeroimpact project, we aim to develop an innovative, sustainable and automatic method to detect marine species using environmental DNA (eDNA) and metabarcoding.

Accession	PRJNA1032405
Data Type	Raw sequence reads
Scope	Environment
Organism	seawater metagenome [Taxonomy ID: 1561972] unclassified sequences; metagenomes; ecological metagenomes; seawater metagenome
Publications	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Published online: Cornelis I et al., "Environmental DNA for monitoring the impact of offshore wind farms on fish and invertebrate community structures", <i>Environmental DNA</i>, 2024;6(4) 2. Published online: Dukan N et al., "Vertical and horizontal environmental DNA (eDNA) patterns of fish in a shallow and well-mixed North Sea area", <i>Scientific Reports</i>, 2024;14(1)

Two publications linked. Lab sequencing protocols for both appears nearly identical in Methods, but no linkage to a standard protocol.

2.3 eDNA extraction

URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/edn3.575>

DNA extraction of the sampled Sterivex filters was conducted in a laminar flow cabinet in a PCR-free designated room. Before and after use, a 15 min UV-treatment was applied and all surfaces were successively cleaned with 10% bleach and 70% ethanol.

The Sterivex filters were incubated overnight at 56°C in a rotating incubator (Incubator-Genie, Scientific Industries), with 800 µL lysis buffer (718 µL ATL buffer [Qiagen], 80 µL Proteinase K [Qiagen] and 2 µL gBlocks® fragments IPC [1/10,000] [Integrated DNA Technologies]). After transferring the lysis buffer into a 5.0 mL LoBind tube (Eppendorf), extraction was performed using the DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's protocol. After washing, eDNA was eluted in two steps in a total volume of 100 µL TE buffer (70°C). Three extraction negative controls were included by applying the same protocol on blank 0.45-µm Sterivex filters. In total 144 filters were extracted. The obtained eDNA extracts were subsequently quantified with the QuantiFluor® dsDNA System (Promega), according to the protocol provided, and stored at -20°C until further processing.

2.4 Library preparation

Paper from Cornelis et al. (2024)

A one-step amplification protocol was used for library preparation. The PCR amplification was performed using fusion primers (Sigma Aldrich), which contained the template specific primer sequence and a unique barcode tag of 6 to 10 nucleotides. The PCR reactions were performed in triplicate in a total volume of 25 µL containing 12.5 µL KAPA HiFi Hotstart 2x ReadyMix (Roche), 0.5 µL Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) (10 mg/µL), 1 µL of each primer (2.5 µM), 7 µL UltraPure™ water (Invitrogen™) and 3 µL extracted eDNA. Six (12S) and eight (COI) PCR negative controls were included by replacing the extracted eDNA with 3 µL of UltraPure™ water.

The 12S target sequence was amplified using the MiFish primers developed by Miya et al. (2015) which target a 163–185 bp region of the mitochondrial 12S rDNA. The universal forward and reverse primer pair (MiFish_U) were degenerated to simultaneously target Osteichthyes and Clasmobranchs (MiFish_U/E_F: 5'-GT(C/T)GGTAA(A/V/T)CTCGTGCCAGC-3'; MiFish_U/E_R: 5'-CATAGTGGGGTATCTAATCC(C/T)AGTTTG-3'). The COI target sequence was amplified using the miCOLintF and jgHCO2198 primers designed by Leray et al. (2013). These primers target a 313 bp fragment of the COI gene that is especially suited to distinguish between metazoan species.

The reactions were run on a Bio-Rad T100™ thermal cycler and began with 3 min of denaturation at 95°C, 40 cycles of denaturation for 20 s at 98°C, annealing for 15 s at 62°C and elongation for 15 s at 72°C, and ended with a final elongation step of 5 min at 72°C for the 12S barcode. The COI barcode was amplified with an initial denaturation of 3 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of denaturation for 30 s at 98°C, annealing for 30 s at 54°C and elongation for 30 s at 72°C, and ended with a final elongation of 5 min at 72°C. From each of the technical replicates, a subset was quality checked on the Bioanalyzer (2100 Bioanalyzer, Agilent) according to the protocol provided with the Agilent DNA 7500 Kit.

In the post-PCR lab, the three PCR replicates were combined into separate pools. For the 12S barcode each of the 150 uniquely indexed samples from each PCR replicate were pooled into three separate pools. For COI only 98 unique indexed primer pairs were available for sample tagging. The 41 samples, including eight negative controls, from the September field campaign were prepared with samples for another project. The 111 samples, including 17 negative controls, from the November field campaign were prepared in two separate 96-well plates. The three PCR replicates were then pooled into nine separate pools so that samples with identical barcode tags could be distinguished by the use of unique adapter tags for each pool. From each PCR product 5 µL (12S) or 15 µL (COI) was added into a 1.5 mL LoBind tube (Eppendorf). Each pool of uniquely tagged PCR products was purified using magnetic CleanNGS beads (CleanNA), by adding 1x (12S) or 0.8x (COI) of the total volume of the pool. On the magnetic holder the beads were washed twice with 60 µL of 80% ethanol. Elution of the purified PCR-products was performed in 100 µL (12S) or 50 µL (COI) of 10 mM Tris-HCl buffer at pH 8.5. After purification, the three 12S and nine COI pools were quality checked with the Bioanalyzer.

At the Admera Health Biopharma Services (NJ, USA) the PCR-pools were ligated with the Illumina TruSeq adapters and pooled into one 12S pool and two COI pools. The 2 × 300 bp paired-end sequencing of the three pools was performed using three flowcells on the Illumina MiSeq platform. The raw sequencing data was demultiplexed for each of the technical PCR replicates.

From the GBIF occurrence record, we must follow 3 links to get to paper/s describing the non-standardised sequencing protocols: GBIF → SRA → BioProject → publication)

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Sample data

GBIF sample occurrence record → NCBI BioSample

URL:

<https://https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4599151607>

MaterialSample	Interpreted	Original
Material sample ID	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110320 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110321 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110322	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110320 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110321 https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN38110322

Material samples linked directly (in three replicates)

National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMEA14201105>

BioSample

Full ▾

13_1_DYF_NJ2021

Identifiers BioSample: SAMN38110320; Sample name: 112_095_220202_999_2988_455_01_3331; SRA: SRS1970887

Organism [seawater metagenome](#)
unclassified entries; unclassified sequences; metagenomes; ecological metagenomes

Package [MIMARKS: survey_water_version 6.0](#)

Attributes

collection date	2021-09-22
depth	bottom
broad-scale environmental context	marine
local-scale environmental context	Coastal
environmental medium	seawater
geographic location	Belgium: North Sea
latitude and longitude	51.23635 N 2.816283 E
negative control type	not applicable
sample collection device or method	Niskin carousel
sample material processing	MiFish_U/E_F-tag/MiFish_U/E_R-tag
sample size	2000
sample volume or weight for DNA extraction	900
size fraction selected	0.45
total depth of water column	18.4608
Repeat experiment	13 1 1

Description Keywords: GSC:MixS;MIMARKS:6.0

BioProject [PRJNA1032405](#) Seawater from the North Sea
Retrieve [all samples](#) from this project

Submission Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Isabelle Cornelis, 2025-11-06

Sample type, collection date, location, experimental details, identifying person